

Diabetes Risk Assessment of Undergraduate Clinical Students of a Medical School in the Southeast Region of Nigeria. The Preliminary Results

M.O. Nkpozi , U.N. Onwuchekwa, B.C. Ubani Ukoma,
F.C. Okezie

Department of Internal Medicine, Abia State University Teaching Hospital, ABSUTH, Aba, Nigeria

Abstract

Background and Objective: Diabetes mellitus (DM), a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease, is increasing in prevalence in the sub-Saharan Africa region. Many individuals still remain undiagnosed in our setting despite the risk factors being well documented. Published literature on the risk of diabetes mellitus in a cohort of young clinical students in the southeast region of Nigeria is scanty. This study, therefore, set out to bridge this gap in knowledge.

Subjects and Methods: This was a prospective descriptive study in which data about risk of developing diabetes mellitus over the next 10 years was assessed in fifth year medical students of Abia State University Teaching Hospital (ABSUTH), Aba using the well validated FINDRISC questionnaire tool from August 1, 2024 to September 30, 2024. Relevant data which included the parameters of the FINDRISC score tool obtained were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 software.

Results: A total of 220 clinical students participated in the study, made up of 116 (52.7%) male students and 104 (47.3%) female students. About 104 (47.3%) of the students were overweight/obese. Differences in the body mass indices (BMI) of the male and female students was not statistically significant. The highest diabetes risk score of the students was within 11-16 which was not up to 17-20 at which the participants had the least risk of having DM over the next 10 years.

Conclusion: The 10-year risk of suffering DM by the clinical students was not significant but a considerable number of them were overweight/obese. It is recommended that these students exercise regularly to prevent the resultant overweight/obesity and thus prevent type 2 DM in the future.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyperglycaemia due to reduced insulin secretion by the beta cells of the pancreas, decreased glucose utilization by the target tissues (insulin resistance) and increased hepatic glucose production [1]. Diabetes mellitus is a leading cause of non-communicable disease. The prevalence of DM is increasing [2], more so, in the sub Saharan African region [3] due to ageing of the population, improving survival of people living with diabetes, obesity, increased urbanization and westernization, dietary changes and physical inactivity.

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) account for 90-95% of all cases of DM worldwide [4]. An interplay of genetic

susceptibility and environmental/lifestyles factors such as high fat/carbohydrate low fibre diet, physical inactivity leading to overweight/obesity is thought to be driving the global pandemic of T2DM [5]. About 78% of people in Africa who are diabetic remain undiagnosed and do not know they are living with DM [6]. It is projected by the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) that the number of people living with diabetes is expected to rise from 366 million people in 2011 to 552 million by 2030 if nothing is being done to check it. In sub-Saharan Africa, the proportion of people with undiagnosed DM [6] is up to 90%.

In their systemic review and meta-analysis, [7] noted that the overall pooled prevalence of DM in Nigeria was 5.77% (95% CI 4.3-7.1) with the prevalence varying

More Information

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from 3.0% in the North West zone to 9.8% in the South south zone. In the same report, the identified risk factors [7] for T2DM included a family history of T2DM, urban dwelling, unhealthy dietary habits, cigarette smoking, older age, physical inactivity and resultant obesity [7]. According to a recent International Diabetes Federation (IDF) report in 2011, the estimated DM prevalence in Nigeria was 4.04% compared to Reunion which had the highest prevalence in Africa at 16.78%, Benin (1.71%), Ghana (4.09%), Niger (4.36%), Cameroun (5.18) and South Africa (6.46%) [6].

All over the world, the increasing prevalence of type 2 DM is driven by an increase in the adult population, increased longevity, increased urbanization and consumption of high energy caloric diets [8]. This, coupled with reduced physical activity, result to obesity/overweight [8]. With this increasing prevalence of DM in Sub-Saharan Africa, there is, thus, an urgent need to intervene to arrest the trend. Efforts aimed at mitigating this trend of DM should be targeted at individuals at high risk of DM and such individuals are identified using multivariate risk scores [9]. It is important to state that diabetes risk scoring tools are available and have been used successfully to prevent, treat and manage DM [10]. Some of the risk scoring tools [9] include the Finnish Diabetes Risk Score (FINDRISC), Framingham Risk Score, United Kingdom Diabetes Risk Score, American Diabetes Association Risk Score (ADARISC), Canadian Diabetes Risk Score (CANDRISC) and Indian Diabetes Risk Score (IDRISC) and they are quite effective in predicting individuals at risk of DM. The FINDRISC tool appears to be most commonly used because it is simple, noninvasive, easy to use, cheap, reliable and fast [9]; performing excellently well in the 10-year prediction of risk of DM and has been validated in European and Nigerian populations [11-17]. The FINDRISC tool has been used to screen and identify individuals at high risk for undetected T2DM, abnormal glucose tolerance and metabolic syndrome [17]. There is a concern about utilizing most of the other diabetes risk score outside the FINDRISC tool in young adult population [18]. This is why we assessed the diabetes risk susceptibility of the undergraduate medical students who have some level of diabetes and general health education using the FINDRISC questionnaire tool.

With increasing diabetes education, use of the Nigerian National guideline and the current practice guideline of the American Diabetes Association for the management of diabetes mellitus, healthcare workers and clinical students are now more knowledgeable about DM prevention practices. The objective of this study, therefore, was to assess the risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus over 10 years among clinical students in Abia state, South East Nigeria. Data generated from this study will be useful to clinicians,

policy makers, government and managers of health institutions to guide T2DM prevention practices and appropriate healthcare budgeting leading to appropriate allocation of healthcare resources and services.

Subjects and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This was a prospective observational study carried out on male and female fifth year medical clinical students of Abia State University, Uturu, who were aged 18 years and above. Aba is a commercial city in the Southeast region of Nigeria known for her industrial, mercantile and craftwork activities. The hospital is the largest tertiary health facility in Aba and gets referrals from all the primary and secondary health facilities in Aba and the neighboring states. The medical students (male and female) undergo their clinical training/experience at the teaching hospital located in Aba. The Department of Internal Medicine, ABSUTH, Aba has Consultants in seven subspecialties with complement resident doctors and house officers.

Inclusion Criteria

All the students were administered the well validated FINDRISC questionnaire except for those who did not want to participate as subjects in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Students who were diagnosed diabetic prior to the study and those that did not sign the consent form were excluded from the study.

Subjects Recruitment and Data Collection

From August 1, 2024 to September 30, 2024, all the students that met the inclusion criteria for the study were enrolled in the study. A total of 220 fifth year medical students responded to the self-administered FINDRISC questionnaire after several sessions of education by two trained educators. Data for the study included their ages and gender and the student's responses to the FINDRISC questionnaire. From the latter, their individual diabetes risk scores were calculated from the 8 components which included their ages, body mass index, waist circumference, physical activity, consumption of vegetables, fruits and berries, use of antihypertensives, previous diagnosis of high blood glucose and a family history of diabetes mellitus.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from Abia state university teaching hospital's Health Research Ethics Committee before commencing the study.

Statistical Analysis of Data

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Inc. Chicago IL. USA) version 23.0 statistical software was used for data analysis. For continuous variables such as the ages of the study participants, mean values and standard deviations (SD) were calculated and the means compared using independent two samples t-test. Categorical variables such as the frequency of the

sex were summarized using proportions expressed in percentages. The categorical variables were compared using the non-parametric test, chi square test. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 220 medical students, 116 males (52.7%) and 104 females (47.3%) enrolled in the study. The body mass indices of the students are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Body Mass Indices of the Medical Students

BMI	Underweight	Normal eight	Overweight	Obesity
Gender:				
Male	2	30	24	2
Female	3	23	20	6
Total	5	53	44	8

Key: BMI = body mass index

A considerable number of the students (47.3%) were overweight/obese. Differences in the BMI of the male and female medical students was not statistically significant ($p=0.366$). The mean diabetes risk score of

the students was 6.07 ± 3.17 and the difference between the mean diabetes risk score of the male and female medical students was not statistically significant ($t = -1.22, p = 0.224$).

Table 2: The Diabetes Risk Scores of the Medical Students

DRS	≤ 3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10-16
Male	30	28	2	28	8	0	2	18
Female	24	20	0	22	8	4	4	22
Total	54	48	2	50	16	4	6	40

Key: DRS = diabetes risk score for the students

The highest diabetes risk score of the medical students was within 10 - 16 which was not up to 17-20 at which the participants had the least risk of having DM over the next 10 years. Again, 190(86.4%) and 196 (89.1%) of the students were not eating fruits/vegetable and had a sedentary lifestyle respectively.

Discussion

The main findings of this study were that majority of the students adopted a sedentary lifestyle which (directly or indirectly) subsequently resulted in a significant number of them being overweight and obese. Again, the 10-year future diabetes risk of the medical students was very low and the mean diabetes risk score of the students was 6.07 ± 3.17 .

In the index study, 47.3% of the study participants (medical students) were overweight/obese; this is similar to the 43.2% reported overweight/obesity in a population based cohort study [19] carried out to assess the risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus among young adults (aged 15-35) in Asaba, Delta state, Nigeria using the validated FINDRISC tool. Finding of overweight/obesity in these comparable young persons could be because of the high level of sedentary lifestyles noted in the two studies. Overweight/obesity in these young men and women is worrisome knowing that it is a strong risk factor for DM and other cardiovascular diseases in the near future. This report of 47.3% overweight/obesity was comparable to the 48.1% overweight/obesity noted by [20] in a much larger study involving 58,567 participants in Ogun state.

However, in the Ogun study [20], more females had increased BMI unlike in the current study where equal number of males and females had raised BMI

In the current study, the mean diabetes risk score of the clinical students was 6.07 ± 3.17 with a range of 3 to 16. This is slightly lower than the mean diabetes risk score of 7.4 ± 5.4 with a range of 0.0-24.0 reported in the study by [21] in Ebonyi state, Nigeria. In this same study carried out in Ebonyi state, the 10-year risk categorization of respondents showed that 57.9% had a low risk of DM in contrast to the study done in Ogun state [20] where about 5.05% had high risk of developing DM over the subsequent 10 years. This mean diabetes risk score in the present study was, however, slightly more than the 5.60 ± 3.90 reported by [20] in Ogun state in which the female participants had a higher mean score of 6.34 ± 4.16 vs $4.24 \pm 3.71, p < 0.05$. In all these studies in Ogun [20], Ebonyi [21] and Aba in Abia state, the risk of developing DM is low in all of them, hence prompting the urgent need to implement and strengthen the diabetes preventive strategies.

The 10-year risk of developing DM in the index study was very low and this contrasts sharply with the reports of similar studies carried out among young adult populations in Nigeria [19] and Jordan [18]. A report of 12.0% moderate risk and 1.5% high risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus was reported in the Nigerian population [19] just as 5.2% moderate risk and 1.8% high risk of T2DM was reported in the study conducted among young students in Jordan [18]. In contrast, in

another study conducted in Onitsha [17], Nigeria, among a more elderly population of local government employees, 9% of the study population had a high risk of developing DM over the next 10 years. This is comparable to the 5.05% of the study population with risk of DM within the next 10 years as reported by [20] in Ogun state, Nigeria. This is probably because of the similarity in the socio-demographic distribution of the Ogun [20] state and Onitsha [17] studies.

Finally, in the index study, about 196 (89.1%) of the students were identified as living a sedentary lifestyle; a lifestyle devoid of physical activities of more than thirty minutes for at least five times every week. This is so even though this population is supposed to be active and physically active in the society. No wonder, then, a large percentage of the students had overweight/obesity in their youths. It is pertinent to note that the diabetes risk score was more in the females in the Ogun [20], Asaba [19], Ebonyi [21] and the index study in Aba. It is, also, important to note that this study was intended to include the final year medical students but was discontinued when the preliminary results were obtained and analyzed.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has shown that the 10-year risk of suffering diabetes mellitus by the clinical students of Abia State University, Aba was very low and that a significant number of them was obese/overweight resulting from sedentary lifestyle. It is, therefore, recommended that prevention, early detection and effective management of T2DM risk factors be pursued via general health education, diabetes risk reduction and diabetes education to reduce morbidity and mortality from DM. Persons with DM or who are at increased diabetes risk need early detection and management using counseling and medications as appropriate

Conflicts of Interest

Nil

Author's Contributions

Dr Marcellinus O. Nkpozi - Conception and design of the research, drafting of the manuscript and taking care of the overall responsibility for the study.

Drs Okezie FC, Madu GO, Ohanusi PO and Barrah JE – collection, collation and analysis of the data.

Dr Ubani Ukoma BC - interpretation of the data and statistical analysis.

Dr UN Onwuchekwa - Final approval and critical revision of the manuscript.

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